

Role of complex nutrients, vitamins and amino acids on alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase activity during acetic acid production by an ethanol resistant strain of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀

Modhurima Chakraborti* and Ajit Kumar Banik

Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Calcutta, 92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : modhurima_chakraborty@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : Complex nutrients are composed of different vitamins, amino acids and minerals. Addition of such components in the production media of acetic acid can increase the yield affecting the two main regulatory enzymes alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase and also makes it cost effective due to easy availability. In the present study, soyabean meal has proved its maximum effectivity by increasing the acetic acid production upto 13.46 g/L and cell weight upto 4.48 g/L. Vitamins like – nicotinic acid and D-biotin and amino acids such as – L-tryptophan and L-glutamic acid also showed their effectivity. Other vitamins and amino acids had negligible effect on both acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase.

Keywords : Acetic acid, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, complex nutrients, vitamins, amino acids.

Introduction

Acetic acid is an important feedstock for many chemicals, such as – sodium acetate is used as an acidulant and as a meat spray to inhibit microbial growth. Calcium magnesium acetate (CMA) has been identified by the US Federal Highway Administration as an environmentally safe and non corrosive deicer for use of roads in winter and potassium acetate was identified as a heat exchange fluid¹⁻³. At present these products are made from petroleum derived acetic acid at a cost of about \$ 650 per ton. Fermentation is potentially a cost effective alternative for acetic acid production. Production of acetic acid via fermentation using renewable biomass feedstock has been studied extensively since late 1970s^{1,3-7}.

However, one obstacle to the successful commercialization of this process is the expensive nutrients required in this medium. If a low cost medium can supply all the nutritional requirements (like, nitrogen sources, vitamins, amino acids and trace elements) to sustain viability and productivity, then it would be economically feasible to produce acetates by fermentation⁸.

The present study has been designed to show the effect of the complex nutrients from both plant and animal

origin, vitamins and amino acids on the activity of the two main enzymes of acetic acid production i.e. alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase, because, these are the cheap sources of different vitamins, amino acids and minerals, highly required for satisfactory growth and productivity of our desired organism.

Materials and methods :

Microorganism used :

Saccharomyces cerevisiae AB₁₀₀, a newly isolated ethanol resistant strain in our laboratory have been used in these studies^{9,10}.

Medium and cultural condition :

The maintenance media consisted of 1% D-glucose, 0.5% peptone, 0.5% yeast extract and 4% agar agar powder. pH was adjusted to 5.0. Organism was maintained at 30 °C for 48 h. Inoculum was harvested by washing the slant with sterile distilled water, the cell density to 2.05×10^5 per ml. The medium for fermentation consisted of 10% D-glucose, 0.125% KH₂PO₄, 0.5% (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.05% MgSO₄·7H₂O and 10 µg/ml of each of FeSO₄·7H₂O, MnSO₄·H₂O and ZnSO₄·7H₂O. pH was adjusted to 4.5. Both medium were sterilized at 121 °C

and 15 lb/inch² pressure for 15 min. 250 ml conical flask containing 85 ml of the fermentation medium was inoculated with 5 ml (1.025×10^6 cell/ml) of inoculum and incubated at 30 °C for 96 h. After fermentation, the cell was separated by centrifugation and the supernatant was used for the analysis of acetic acid and determination of enzyme activity¹⁰.

Estimation of acetic acid :

Concentration of acetic acid was determined by HPLC with a TPS Spectra System apparatus using a Biorad Aminex HPX-87H column heated to 40 °C and a Refraction Index Detector (Waters 640). The mobile phase was 0.005 M sulfuric acid flowing at 0.4 ml/min^{10,11}.

Assay of alcohol dehydrogenase :

0.1 ml of supernatant was added to the mixture of 15 mM β -NAD⁺, 50 mM sodium pyrophosphate buffer (pH 8.8) and 95% ethanol and incubated for 6 min at 25 °C in a suitably thermostated spectrophotometer. Absorbance was recorded at 340 nm. Enzyme activity was expressed as μ /ml. One unit of enzyme activity represents the amount of enzyme which can convert 1.0 μ mole of ethanol to acetaldehyde per minute at pH 8.8 at 25 °C^{10,12}.

Assay of aldehyde dehydrogenase :

0.1 ml of supernatant was added to the mixture of 20 mM β -NAD⁺, 1 (M) Tris-HCl buffer (pH 8.0), 100 mM acetaldehyde solution, 3 (M) KCl and 1 (M) 2-mercaptoethanol and incubated for 5 min at 25 °C in a suitably thermostatted spectrophotometer. Absorbance was recorded at 340 nm. Enzyme activity was expressed as μ /ml. One unit of enzyme activity represents the amount of enzyme which can oxidize 1.0 μ mole of acetaldehyde to acetic acid per minute at pH 8.0 at 25 °C in presence of β -NAD⁺, potassium and thiols^{10,13}.

Preparation of complex nutrients :

(i) *Preparation of paddy soak liquor* : 130–150 g (140 g taken) of paddy were thoroughly washed with 400 ml distilled water for 15 min. The purpose of washing is to remove the mud and the extraneous material adhering to paddy.

The washed paddy was then dipped in 200 ml of hot distilled water (55 °C) and was allowed to soak water for 2 h at about 55 °C. When the grain swelled completely, the soaked water was filtered through cotton. It was then

sterilized in autoclave at 15 lb/inch² pressure for 15 min and then stored at 4 °C. The solid content was found to be 2.1 g/100 ml¹⁴.

(ii) *Preparation of wheat bran and rice bran extract* : 20 g of bran (free from mud) were taken in 200 ml of hot distilled water (55 °C) in a 500 ml beaker.

The suspension were kept at 55 °C for 18 h. The extract was filtered through cotton and then sterilized in autoclave and stored at 4 °C. The solid content of wheat bran and rice bran extract were 11.54 g/100 ml and 1.08 g/100 ml respectively.

(iii) *Preparation of corn steep liquor* : 100 g of corn were taken in 250 ml of distilled water containing 0.52% of potassium meta bisulfite in a 500 ml beaker and heated in an controlled water bath for 48 h at temperature of 50–55 °C (18 h in boiling water bath). The steep water was filtered off and then concentrated approximately to 50% solid content by evaporation by vacuum. It was then sterilized at 15 lb/inch² pressure for 15 min and stored at 4 °C. The solid content was found to be 2.68 g/100 ml¹⁴.

(iv) *Preparation of soya bean meal* : 500 g of soya bean were made fat free by alcohol distillation.

100 g of soybean taken in a 1 L beaker, containing 300 ml of hot (55 °C) double distilled water. This suspension was kept at 55 °C for 18 h. The extract was then filtered through cotton and sterilized at 15 lb/inch² pressure for 15 min at 121 °C. The solid content was found to be 4.6 g/100 ml¹⁴.

Discussion

Results of cell growth, acetic acid production and enzyme activity in media containing different complex nutrients are presented in Figs. 1 to 4 respectively. It was observed that, amongst the complex nutrients of plant origin, only soyabean meal showed significant improvement in acetic acid production and growth rate, whereas four out of five complex nutrients of animal origin, showed significant production and growth rate. The better yield was probably due to the presence of certain nutrients in soyabean meal. It is generally a rich source of nitrogen, water soluble vitamins, amino acids, minerals, other growth stimulants and approximately 4.6% solids.

It was also observed that, specific composition of a complex nutrient influenced the enzyme activity and acid production. The results indicated that L-tryptophan might

have some useful role due to the participation in coenzyme Q biosynthesis, one of the major components of energy yielding process in mitochondria. Amongst other amino acids, L-glutamic acid showed stimulatory effect, when supplemented at a concentration of 0.75 mg/ml.

Effects of some water-soluble vitamins on acetic acid production are given in Table 1. Nicotinic acid and D-biotin showed significant stimulatory effect. This was in accordance with the fact, that soyabean meal, which gen-

erally contains a number of water soluble vitamins, showed prominent stimulatory effect in the present study. However, stimulatory effect of individual vitamins or amino acids on acetic acid production didn't exceed the stimulatory effect of the complex nutrients, since synergistic effect of all these biomolecules would be essential for their proper functioning. Complex nutrients might provide such synergism. Such complex nutrients will definitely take care of economical aspects when applied in large scale industrial processes.

Results

Table 1. Effect of vitamins on alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase during acetic acid production by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀

Vitamin	Concentration (µg/ml)	Cell weight (g/100 ml)	Acetic acid (g/100 ml)	Activity of alcohol dehydrogenase (mu/ml)	Activity of aldehyde dehydrogenase (mu/ml)
Nicotinic acid	Control	0.4023 ± 0.01	1.0962 ± 0.03	115.03 ± 4.02	53.38 ± 3.12
	0.5	0.4235 ± 0.02	1.1571 ± 0.01	117.62 ± 3.05	56.83 ± 1.55
	0.75	0.4329 ± 0.02	1.1710 ± 0.02	118.24 ± 4.11	57.77 ± 5.01
	1.0	0.4429 ± 0.03	1.1763 ± 0.02	119.03 ± 2.87	58.3 ± 4.35
	1.5	0.4282 ± 0.01	1.1309 ± 0.03	117.37 ± 2.46	55.73 ± 2.22
<i>para</i> -Amino benzoic acid	Control	0.4023 ± 0.01	1.0962 ± 0.04	115.03 ± 5.11	53.38 ± 1.98
	0.2	0.3411 ± 0.03	1.0857 ± 0.02	112.11 ± 5.00	50.11 ± 2.76
	0.5	0.3388 ± 0.03	1.0642 ± 0.03	111.88 ± 3.42	49.88 ± 4.13
D-Biotin	Control	0.4023 ± 0.05	1.0962 ± 0.04	115.03 ± 3.22	53.38 ± 1.88
	0.5	0.4658 ± 0.02	1.1025 ± 0.01	111.52 ± 4.35	49.25 ± 2.11
	1.0	0.4705 ± 0.03	1.1083 ± 0.03	109.63 ± 5.02	47.36 ± 3.01
Pyridoxine-HCl	Control	0.4023 ± 0.02	1.0962 ± 0.04	115.03 ± 5.22	53.38 ± 1.96
	0.2	0.2929 ± 0.01	1.0720 ± 0.02	112.29 ± 4.51	50.92 ± 2.02
	0.5	0.2494 ± 0.03	1.0405 ± 0.02	107.64 ± 3.95	47.46 ± 3.11
	1.0	0.2364 ± 0.02	1.0321 ± 0.01	106.05 ± 4.03	46.5 ± 3.21

Data shows the average value ±SD (n = 3).

Other vitamins such as - Vitamin B₁₂, Ca-pantothenate, Riboflavine, etc. showed very little stimulatory effect on acetic acid production and on the activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase.

Table 2. Effect of amino acids on alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase during acetic acid production by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀

Amino acid	Concentration (µg/ml)	Cell weight (g/100 ml)	Acetic acid (g/100 ml)	Activity of alcohol dehydrogenase (mu/ml)	Activity of aldehyde dehydrogenase (mu/ml)
Glutamic acid	Control	0.4023 ± 0.01	1.0962 ± 0.02	115.03 ± 5.11	53.38 ± 1.55
	0.5	0.4129 ± 0.02	1.109 ± 0.03	116.71 ± 2.32	54.17 ± 2.02
	0.75	0.4157 ± 0.01	1.1113 ± 0.03	118.23 ± 3.17	56.32 ± 3.12
	1.0	0.3176 ± 0.03	1.103 ± 0.01	114.3 ± 4.82	52.03 ± 1.67

Table-2 (contd.)

L-Lysine-HCl	Control	0.4023 ± 0.01	1.0962 ± 0.04	115.03 ± 2.98	53.38 ± 1.89
	0.5	0.32 ± 0.02	1.0221 ± 0.02	109.17 ± 3.64	47.71 ± 1.63
	1.0	0.3105 ± 0.01	1.0077 ± 0.03	108.53 ± 3.55	46.35 ± 2.74
L-Aspartic acid	0.5	0.3317 ± 0.03	1.0329 ± 0.01	110.07 ± 4.54	48.7 ± 3.52
	1.0	0.28 ± 0.02	1.0025 ± 0.02	107.28 ± 5.42	45.82 ± 1.44
Tryptophan	Control	0.4023 ± 0.00	1.0962 ± 0.02	115.03 ± 5.11	53.38 ± 2.63
	0.3	0.4105 ± 0.01	1.0988 ± 0.01	118.2 ± 4.83	56.02 ± 3.00
	0.4	0.4247 ± 0.03	1.1312 ± 0.03	122.12 ± 3.93	60.21 ± 1.11
	0.5	0.3723 ± 0.01	1.1045 ± 0.02	117.23 ± 5.05	45.32 ± 3.52

Data shows the average value ±SD (n = 3).

Other amino acids such as - L-glycine, L-alanine, L-cysteine, L-arginine-HCl, L-leucine, DL-phenyl alanine, L-proline, L-valine and L-histidine showed very minimal effect on the activity of two main enzymes alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase and simultaneously on acetic acid production.

Fig. 1. Effect of beef extract on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀.

Fig. 2. Effect of malt extract on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀.

Fig. 3. Effect of soybean meal on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀.

Fig. 4. Effect of tryptone on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀.

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